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<i>Abstract</i>	The central element is the creation of an acceleration services catalogue under Work Package 2 (WP2), involving stakeholders like university alliances and FOR-EU. The project also conducts a comparative analysis of strategies employed by European Alliances within the EUI, ultimately aiming to bridge the gap between institutional transformations and acceleration services in European higher education and research. The document follows a structured approach, covering the transformation agenda, services exploration, the initial catalogue, and concluding with insights

History of changes

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Document Updates

This revised version of the deliverable incorporates the feedback from the European Commission, addressing the following inquiries:

The deliverable provides a preliminary description of an initial set of acceleration services that are expected to compose the project's catalogue to be implemented in the planned Agora.

The set of services reported are a starting baseline and are obtained after the analysis of the outcomes of Deliverable D4.1.

However, the document insufficiently describes the methodology through which they have been identified for inclusion in the first set of services to be developed nor how they relate to the Business processes defined in D4.1.

The documents needs to be revised in order to clarify these aspects and give to the reader a better understanding about who are the stakeholders having made the identification, what was their profile and why these services have been identified as valuable in terms of matching of the needs and generating the expected project impact and how they relate to the outcomes of D4.1.

The document now explicitly addresses these comments:

In order to effectively address the Commission's concerns and enhance the deliverable's clarity, significant improvements have been made.

Notably, two critical sections have been added to the document: 4 Preliminary Analysis Methodology, which includes subparts such as Stakeholder Consultation, Selection Criteria, and Future Plans. These additions offer a comprehensive overview of the rigorous process undertaken to identify the initial set of acceleration services. Additionally, a second section

titled 5 Dynamic Methodology for Acceleration Services Development: A Comprehensive Plan has been incorporated, outlining a detailed roadmap consisting of seven strategic steps.

Furthermore, we've improved the overall clarity of all documents by incorporating relevant information in the pre-existing sections.

Abbreviation list

aUPaEU	A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities
D4.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D10 from WP4, Inventory, Action plan and preliminary set of processes
D5.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D12 from WP5, Report on the implementation gap analysis and the ideation of the digital transition
D7.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D18 from WP7, First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholders mapping
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
EUI	European Universities Initiative
FOR-EU	Forum of European University Alliances
MVS	Minimum Viable Solution
TTO	Technological Transfer Offices

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1 Introduction

The aUPaEU project is a collaborative effort among five distinguished research universities with extensive expertise in Higher Education Institution (HEI) networks and alliances. Its primary goal is to facilitate the institutional transformation of HEIs across Europe, particularly those engaged in the [European Universities Initiative](#) (EUI). This transformation aims to align research policies, promote cross-border collaboration, and create a unified European Research and Innovation (R&I) landscape, commonly called the European Research Area (ERA).

The aUPaEU project recognizes the need for acceleration services to expedite this transformative process. Drawing inspiration from the startup ecosystem, acceleration services have proven to be catalysts for growth and innovation. In the context of HEIs, these services encompass a range of support mechanisms, including mentorship, networking, funding access, educational programs, and more. By integrating these services into the higher education sector, the project aims to accelerate institutional transformations and contribute to the establishment of a single European market for R&I.

One of the objectives (OBJ1) of the aUPaEU Project is the creation of an acceleration services catalogue, and this deliverable proposes an initial one, from the work performed during the first year of the project.

This catalogue is not merely a directory of services offered by universities; it is a compilation and deployment of innovative research and innovation initiatives that currently are under development. When universities seek or provide services, they should find representation in this catalogue. If a service does not yet exist, it will be created. The catalogue will consist of collections of related offers, reflecting a collaborative approach to HEI transformation.

The creation of this collection is a complex task and will be the result of Work Package 2 (WP2) within the project. Following the Design Thinking Approach, WP2 will involve empathising with stakeholders, including those engaged in collaborative research initiatives such as university alliances, initially Unite!, EPICUR and other projects (such as our two sister projects CATALISI and Accelerate Future HEI) and looking to a broader audience afterward, such as the Forum of European University Alliances (FOR-EU). The development of a Services Catalogue stands as a crucial milestone in our journey of transformation. We are dedicated to involving stakeholders, tackling obstacles, and realising our goals to shape the trajectory of European higher education and research. This includes enhancing various aspects of institutional transformation, such as sharing infrastructure, and resources, improving the attractiveness of academic careers, collaboration with actors in the research and innovation ecosystem, promotion of open science, community engagement, and fostering gender equality. The initial co-creation of services primarily involves prominent HEIs and alliances, as they have the resources to kickstart these tasks. However, considerations have been made to

ensure that these services can be utilised in subsequent iterations across widening countries.

The catalogue will undergo iterative testing and validation by WP6. This proactive approach ensures more robust interconnection between the various work packages within the project.

Furthermore, WP2 will also conduct a comparative analysis of strategies and means employed by European Alliances within the EUI. By examining decision-making processes, collaborative efforts, and innovative approaches, the project seeks to assess the effective implementation of defined objectives. This analysis aims to provide nuanced perspectives that enhance understanding of the impact and effectiveness of these strategic decisions.

The aUPaEU project represents a significant initiative to facilitate the institutional transformation of HEIs in Europe. By bridging the gap between institutional transformations and acceleration services, it aspires to create a unified European Research and Innovation landscape, fostering collaboration and innovation.

The rest of this document follows this structure. In Section 2, we provide the context of the transformation agenda by reviewing its components. Moving on to Section 3, we delve into the description of acceleration services, drawing references from existing literature to elucidate their nature. Section 4 elaborates on the preliminary analysis methodology employed in crafting the initial outline of the acceleration services catalogue, delineating the criteria for inclusion. Following this, Section 5 outlines a dynamic methodology for the development of acceleration services, presenting a comprehensive plan comprising seven strategic steps. In Section 6, we present the initial catalogue of acceleration services, offering detailed descriptions and categorizations for each service. Finally, we conclude with insights and conclusions pertaining to the forthcoming deliverables associated with the service catalogue in Section 7.

2 Context of the transformation agenda

The European Universities Initiative (EUI) is a dynamic program of the European Commission aimed at establishing Transnational University Alliances across Europe. This initiative strategically modernises and internationalises European higher education, fostering innovation and research.

This initiative comprises two distinct parts: Education and Training, through three project calls within the Erasmus+ program, and Research and Innovation (R&I), aligned with the European Research Area (ERA) strategy, this aspect aims at achieving institutional transformation in R&I within European universities, fostering systemic and enduring impact, common strategies, and joint action plans with national co-financing.

The funding for European university alliances is designed to support the following objectives: develop a common research and innovation program, share research infrastructures and

resources, strengthen R&I cooperation with the innovation ecosystem, especially university-business cooperation, enhance the attractiveness of researchers' careers, integrate open science practices, involve citizens and society, and experiment with joint structures and share best practices for systemic impact.

This comprehensive framework outlines the expected outcomes of the European University Initiatives, encompassing various critical dimensions. These include the establishment of a unified Research & Innovation Agenda, entailing the identification of shared challenges, development of action plans, resource allocation, and the scaling of scientific excellence. Additionally, the initiative emphasises the collaborative utilisation of resources and infrastructure, encompassing legal, financial, and digital aspects, alongside the promotion of open science practices. Furthermore, it seeks to strengthen innovation ecosystems through enhanced academia-business cooperation, fostering innovation capacity, and entrepreneurship. Empowering human capital in research is a pivotal component, focusing on diversity, inclusiveness, gender equality, and robust career development for researchers. The integration of open science practices, citizen and societal engagement in research and innovation, and the promotion of collaborative structures and best practices are integral facets. It's worth noting that the precise strategies for achieving these objectives are determined individually by each Alliance, reflecting their unique approaches and contexts.

At the heart of the aUPaEU project lies Action 13 of the European Research Area Policy Agenda (2022–2024), which underscores the imperative of transforming Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This strategic objective aligns harmoniously with the European Commission's Strategic Plan 2020-2024, aimed at forging a unified European Union (EU) marketplace for research, innovation, and technology. This transformative endeavour seeks to harmonise research policies, facilitate the unrestricted movement of researchers and knowledge, and stimulate cross-continental competition, thus breathing new life into the European Research Area (ERA).

Inspired by the dynamics of the startup ecosystem, acceleration services play a pivotal role in expediting the growth of startups, entrepreneurs, and innovative projects. These services encompass diverse forms of support, including mentorship, networking opportunities, and access to funding, catalysing innovation and progress.

The "European Excellence Initiative: Acceleration services in support of universities" opportunity, from the programme Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON), bridges the realms of institutional transformation and acceleration services. This forward-looking initiative extends the scope of acceleration services to encompass cooperation services for Research and Innovation (R&I) within European HEIs, thereby accelerating their institutional metamorphosis. The seamless integration of transformation and acceleration services within the aUPaEU project empowers HEIs, fostering a dynamic and collaborative landscape for research and innovation throughout Europe.

3 Acceleration services description

This section intends to describe acceleration services from a systemised point of view, which enables the deployment and management of the current acceleration services of the initial catalogue and those that will come in the future.

Following the terminology of aUPaEU Deliverable D4.1, acceleration services for Higher Education Institutions are programs, services, infrastructures, or initiatives designed to help and support HEIs in implementing strategies and pathways for institutional transformation.

In order to enable the general description and characterisation of the acceleration services, we have to move to a more general service approach (Bordoloi, 2019). For this purpose, various definitions of service exist in the literature. Nonetheless, the definition that aligns most effectively with the project's scope is:

"A service is an activity or series of activities of more or less intangible nature that normally but not necessarily take place in interactions between customer and service employees and/or physical or goods and/or systems of the service provider which are provided as solutions to customer problems" (Grönroos, 1990)

According to (Fitzsimmons, 2011), the service package is a concept used in service marketing and management to describe a bundle of goods and services that are offered to customers within a particular environment or context, in this case, acceleration services. It encompasses all the elements and components that make up a service offering. The service package helps businesses and organisations understand and communicate the value they provide to their customers. It typically consists of five key features:

Supporting Facility refers to the physical or tangible infrastructure that is necessary to deliver the service. This can include the Agora, and other physical assets, such as rooms, for example.

Facilitating Goods are tangible items that accompany the service and enhance its value. These goods are typically provided to the customer as part of the service. For example, in the shared research infrastructure it would be the physical research infrastructure.

Information is a crucial component of the service package. It includes data, knowledge, and communication that is used to enhance and support the service. Information can be provided in various forms. For instance, the Agora may provide user guides and online support to assist customers in using their acceleration services.

Explicit services are the core, intangible services that customers receive when they engage with a service provider. These are the primary benefits or experiences that customers seek.

For example, the research and infrastructure notice board, to find peers to collaborate in a research proposal.

Implicit services are the additional, often intangible, elements of the service that customers may not explicitly request but still contribute to their overall satisfaction. In the scope of acceleration services, we use the implicit services in the R&I areas of the Higher Education Transformation Agenda such as: (a) empowering HEIs towards developing shared R&I strategies that deliver on Europe's challenges with critical mass; (b) facilitate the sharing of capacity, infrastructure, and resources through collaborative settings, such as the European Universities initiative; (c) improve the attractiveness of researchers' careers, including through reform of the career assessment and incentives regimes; (d) facilitate cooperation with surrounding R&I ecosystem actors; (e) support the transition to knowledge- and digitally-driven HEIs that mainstream Open Science practices and include research and innovation outputs in teaching; (f) engage citizens in solving societal challenges; (g) support institutional change through inclusive gender equality plans.

In summary, the acceleration service package is a comprehensive concept that encompasses both tangible and intangible elements provided to customers in a specific acceleration service environment. Understanding the components of the acceleration service package helps organisations design and deliver services that meet customer needs and expectations effectively. It also aids in marketing and communication efforts by highlighting the value and features of the acceleration service offering.

ITIL, particularly in its latest version, ITIL v4, offers a robust framework of best practices for organisations to effectively design, deliver, and support IT services (Marrone, 2011). Although the term "acceleration services" isn't explicitly defined, ITIL v4 principles can be applied to manage a wide range of IT services, including those related to acceleration. Key principles include creating value, understanding stakeholder roles, and assessing services based on utility and warranty. This document aims to define acceleration services within an acceleration services table, emphasising the collaborative nature of service relationships and the importance of resource management and continual improvement. It acknowledges that achieving desired outcomes involves resource allocation and risk management, with service providers sharing associated risks and costs. The catalogue distinguishes between outputs and outcomes, highlighting the importance of assessing utility and warranty to ensure services meet stakeholder needs and comply with requirements. It plans to describe utility in the initial catalogue and detail warranty aspects in subsequent deliverables, contingent upon the development of the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS).

4 Preliminary analysis methodology

Before presenting the initial outline of the catalogue, it is deemed important to explain what methodology was used to identify this preliminary set of services regrouped in this deliverable, by using the Empathise Design Thinking approach . This is to facilitate the

reader's understanding into our selection criteria, as well as to give them a better understanding of the stakeholders consulted in the process, explaining the reasons that were put forward to justify this first selection– who was consulted, which profile do they have and why exactly this set was identified.

Our methodology for identifying the initial set of acceleration services is rooted in design thinking methods, which prioritise a predominantly bottom-up approach with elements of top-down input. Starting with the core stakeholders as defined in D7.1, our engagement process was characterised by a collaborative and iterative approach, involving consultations with diverse actors across multiple macro categories, examples of which can be found in Table 3.1 of deliverable D7.1, including Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), research institutions, and university alliances. These consultations were conducted at various levels, including within Grenoble, the Unite! and EPICUR alliances, and within our aUPaEU project team. Although this initial collaboration in crafting services mainly involves prominent HEIs and alliances, steps have been taken to ensure that these services are designed, consulted and suitable for use in widening countries.

Among these consultations, we cultivated a crucial and cooperative partnership with Work Package 4 (WP4), understanding the significance of synergy and joint development between our individual work packages (thus combining the bottom-up approach of WP2 and the top-down one from WP4, which inform the development of the catalogue). Through consistent dialogues and the sharing of ideas with the WP4, we were able to synchronise our initiatives and capitalise on each other's expertise, enhancing our methodology with insights from throughout the project consortium. To elucidate the reciprocal utilisation of inputs and outputs between D4.1 from WP4 and this deliverable from WP2, we can specify that the top-down approach output of D4.1, Section 2, which comprises an inventory of existing acceleration services within HEIs, served as an input for the stakeholders' consultation. Conversely, the output of the bottom-up approach of the stakeholders' consultation, namely the catalogue of acceleration services (Section 6 of this document), was utilised as an input to define the preliminary set of business processes (Section 3 of D4.1). It's worth noting that these consultations correspond to Step 1 outlined in Section 5 of this document, with further details provided in Section 5.1 of D5.1. This said, collaboration and communications with the other WPs is and will continue to be very important for our success. We are dedicated to strengthening these connections to improve collaboration and align our initiatives for collective progress.

4.1 Stakeholder Consultation

Before embarking on stakeholder consultations, preliminary analytical work was conducted to define acceleration services, assess existing offerings, and identify potential areas for development. This preparatory phase was closely linked to the inventory of operating acceleration services (D4.1), analysing current practices, available resources, and gaps in service provision to inform subsequent engagement strategies.

In this first year, our engagement primarily focused on the core stakeholders, comprising members of the project team and the partner universities from the two alliances— as we deemed those entities a logical starting point with whom we have established initial connections and collaborations. Moving forward, we anticipate expanding our outreach to include extended stakeholders, broadening our engagement and ensuring a more comprehensive representation of perspectives and expertise.

Our stakeholder consultation process was guided by insights from the deliverable D7.1 by WP7, which defined core stakeholders and extended stakeholders, focusing mainly on two categories from its Table 3.1.

- HEIs and research institutions
- University Alliances

Within these two categories, we engaged a variety of different profiles of stakeholders, including administrators, administrative staff, faculty members, researchers, and project partners, to gather diverse perspectives on the needed acceleration services within higher education.

Administrators and administrative staff played a crucial role in our consultation, providing valuable insights into institutional priorities, resource constraints, and strategic objectives, which helped to contextualise our selection process. For instance, we consulted with a Vice President for Innovation, as well as administrative staff from valorization and the research support office, who offered key input on institutional priorities and support mechanisms. Faculty members and researchers also contributed significantly by offering perspectives on research and innovation needs, collaboration opportunities, and the support mechanisms necessary for academic success. Our engagement extended to professors and researchers from various levels in partner universities, as well as participants within our own project, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of academic needs and priorities. These stakeholders are actual or potential users of our services or individuals with similar profiles to the target users, thereby validating the relevance and applicability of our offerings.

Our stakeholder consultation process was comprehensive and involved a variety of profiles across different categories. The table below outlines the individuals consulted and their roles:

Profile	Number consulted
Administrators	3
Administrative staff	6
Faculty members	5

Project partners (WP leaders and participants)	12 (6 WP Leaders and 6 participants)
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Our need analysis process involved semi-structured interviews, formal and informal discussions, as well as meetings with the stakeholders mentioned above. We sought to gather diverse perspectives on the acceleration services needed.

The process involved iterative consultations with stakeholders, allowing for the collection of rich and nuanced insights.

- **Five Semi-Structured Interviews, Formal and Informal Discussions:** These were conducted with administrators, administrative staff, faculty, and researchers. The aim was to gather diverse perspectives on acceleration service needs, priorities, and challenges within higher education institutions.
- **Five Meetings:** Within the project itself, initial discussions were held, followed by a structured engagement process using design thinking methodologies. This approach facilitated collaborative problem-solving, idea generation, and alignment of initiatives within the project consortium.

4.2 Selection Criteria

In the process of selecting the initial set of services, we employed a comprehensive approach that combined bottom-up and top-down criteria. These criteria, outlined below, helped ensure that the chosen services would effectively address stakeholders' needs while aligning with institutional goals and priorities.

1. **Value to Stakeholders:** This criterion focused on identifying services that would provide tangible benefits and meet the specific needs, aspirations, and priorities of our stakeholders. To gather insights into stakeholder preferences, we conducted extensive consultations, as described in the previous section. Through these consultations, we gained valuable feedback that informed our selection process.
2. **Feasibility:** Services were evaluated for their feasibility in terms of implementation within the context of our alliances and higher education institutions (HEIs). This assessment took into account various factors, including resource availability, infrastructure requirements, and organisational capacity. Information gathered from approximately 30 meetings with stakeholders throughout 2023, as documented in section 5.1 of D5.1, contributed significantly to our understanding of current implementation needs.
3. **Strategic Alignment:** It was crucial for selected services to align closely with institutional goals, business processes, and strategic priorities. To ensure coherence with the overall mission and vision of our HEIs, we referenced components outlined in

D4.1 during the selection process. By aligning services with strategic objectives, we aimed to maximise their impact and relevance within the institutional context.

By considering these three criteria, we were able to identify a set of acceleration services that not only address stakeholder needs but also align closely with institutional objectives, thereby contributing to the overarching goals of our alliances and HEIs.

4.3 Future Plans

Looking ahead, we recognize the importance of broadening our users' consultation efforts to include additional perspectives and voices from the extended stakeholders group, and include multiple profiles such as students, industry partners, and community members. In line with our commitment to inclusive decision-making, we're placing special emphasis on engaging with FOR-EU. Initially we have attended the FOR-EU on IT & digitalisation meetings held in June and October 2023, being members of the IT & digitalisation subgroup from the beginning. Recognized for their expertise in European projects and higher education policies, collaborating with FOR-EU promises to provide us with valuable insights into successful practices from across Europe. This collaboration will help us develop more effective solutions by drawing from a diverse range of experiences and perspectives. This inclusive approach ensures that our acceleration services are responsive to the diverse needs and aspirations of our users.

Simultaneously, we acknowledge that our methodology for identifying acceleration services is an evolving process, forming part of a multi-year plan aimed at continuously improving and adapting to changing needs and circumstances. As part of our next actions, we intend to expand our examination beyond our immediate context to explore existing practices and initiatives within other alliances and projects. By leveraging insights and lessons learned from diverse sources, we aim to enrich our understanding and inform the development of innovative solutions that can benefit the broader higher education community. This collaborative and forward-thinking approach underscores our commitment to excellence, innovation, and continuous improvement.

In summary, our methodology for identifying the initial set of acceleration services for higher education institutions (HEIs) was founded upon a collaborative and evidence-based approach. Initially, in the first year, we strategically engaged with a closer circle of the core stakeholders group, including academia and project partners, recognizing them as the logical starting point. This approach allowed us to gather valuable insights and establish a strong foundation for our work. Moving forward, our plan is to broaden the circle of stakeholder

consultations, incorporating a wider range of perspectives and expertise from the extended stakeholders groups. (D7.1).

Throughout the process, we carefully considered multiple selection criteria, ensuring that the chosen services are aligned with the business processes and expected impact of HEIs. By integrating stakeholder input, strategic alignment, and impact assessment, we have laid the groundwork for a comprehensive and impactful portfolio of services. These services are poised to support the mission and goals of HEIs and contribute to their success in a rapidly evolving higher education landscape.

5 Dynamic Methodology for Acceleration Services Development: A Comprehensive Plan

In aUPaEU, we proposed to adopt the Design Thinking approach, focusing on the five-phase model proposed by the Hasso Plattner Institute of Design at Stanford, also known as [d.school](#). This approach aligns with our emphasis on applying Design Thinking principles. We've slightly adapted the Design Thinking approach to tailor it to the roles of each WP, resulting in a dynamic seven-step methodology for the development of acceleration services. This methodology loosely aligns with the different WPs of the project and, while not strictly linear, requires that certain steps be completed to fully develop a new acceleration service development.

Table 5.1. Matching five Design Thinking Phase with Corresponding Steps in aUPaEU methodology

Design Thinking Phase	Corresponding Step
Empathise	Step 1: Stakeholder engagement and awareness building (all) Step 2: Requirement analysis and service design (WP2) Step 7: Dissemination (WP7)
Define	Step 3: Data analysis (WP3) Step 4: Business process definition (WP4)
Ideate	Step 5: Implementation (WP5)
Prototype	Step 5: Implementation (WP5)
Test	Step 6: Testing and assessment (WP6)

Figure 1. Acceleration Services Development Methodology

It's relevant to clarify that the methodology employed in the preliminary initial analysis, described in the previous section, was aimed at identifying a preliminary set of services, by using the Empathise phase, whereas the methodology used in the development of acceleration services go through the seven steps, and focus on crafting specific services for individual HEIs or alliances. To illustrate this, we provide two examples.

1. **Acceleration Service #2:** Catalogue of Research Infrastructures:

- In the preliminary analysis methodology, it was determined that this service should be included in the initial acceleration service catalogue.
- In the development methodology, the initial step is to gather the specific requirements for this service. For instance, for the Unite! alliance, a recommendation system powered by artificial intelligence (AI) was deemed necessary to connect researchers for collaboration. Conversely, the [EELISA](#) alliance, following the [EELISA and Unite! Matchmaking Workshop on Sustainability](#), held in 30th November 2023 in Barcelona, expressed the need to include research infrastructures with low [Technological Readiness Levels \(TRL\)](#) in its catalogue. Considering that the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#) does not accept low TRL research infrastructures, these circumstances must be taken into account during service development.

2. **Acceleration Service #4:** Accessing Grants and Funding:

- Similar to the previous service, the preliminary analysis indicated that this service should be part of the preliminary acceleration service catalogue.
- In the development plan, for Unite!, which involved stakeholders from the [IRIS network](#), specific features such as an internal R&I matchmaking noticeboard

and an AI recommendation system fed by various data sources (e.g., [CORDIS](#) open dataset of calls and, additionally, researcher profiles following a Wrocław Tech development, a Unite! partner from Poland) were required.

All these implementations will be documented in D5.2 of WP5 (Report on the Minimum Viable Solutions co-built and tested by user groups), by June 2026.

Below, we delineate the seven steps in this comprehensive plan for acceleration services development.

Step 1: Stakeholder engagement and awareness building

This step, which fits in the Empathise Design Thinking phase, enables the provision of HEIs that can be interested in the use of the Agoras, in order to start the pipeline of the comprehensive plan of acceleration services development, this step can be triggered by any WP action that makes aware of the Agoras to interested stakeholders, or due to a dissemination action or thanks to the website traffic or specific meetings or networking events with relevant stakeholders, giving priority to the matrix top cells of the stakeholders mapping section of D7.1 depicted in its Fig 3.1 Power/interest matrix (reproduced below for convenience). Initially, the core stakeholders were considered and engaged through their respective projects. Examples are Unite! Erasmus+, H2020, and Unite!WIDENING. It is anticipated that extended stakeholders such as sister projects CATALISI and Accelerate Future HEI will be included in the first part of 2024. In addition to the sister projects, the primary emphasis will be on Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in widening countries. If there is substantial interest, HEIs may sign an agreement directly with aUPaEU or through their corresponding project consortium to establish the terms of use and privacy policy for the Agora platform.

Step 2: Requirement analysis and service design (WP2)

The design thinking approach utilised in the requirement analysis and service design phase is pivotal as it lays the groundwork for designing and developing acceleration services in its Empathise phase. Through a series of interviews and both formal and informal discussions with administrators, administrative staff, faculty, and researchers, a comprehensive understanding of the needs within the institution is developed. These interactions help identify the core requirements and priorities, which are crucial for tailoring the services to the specific contexts of higher education institutions.

The collected data is then systematically analysed to identify common themes and unique needs across different departments and faculties. This analysis helps in understanding the diverse perspectives and challenges that stakeholders face, which is critical for ensuring the services developed are both relevant and beneficial.

The outcome of this thorough and collaborative approach is the creation of a detailed user requirements document. This document serves as a blueprint for the subsequent phases of service development, ensuring that all stakeholder needs are considered and addressed in the service design.

Step 3: Data analysis (WP3)

During this stage, which fits in the Define Design Thinking phase, the focus shifts to the data that will support the acceleration services. A detailed examination of data sources, privacy considerations, and the availability of data at different administrative levels (European, national, or regional) is conducted. This step also explores whether the data can be made interoperable across various HEIs, a critical factor for the service's scalability and utility.

Questions about data standardisation and schema are addressed, ensuring that the data used in the services adheres to established standards for data interoperability. This ensures that the services can be integrated seamlessly across different platforms and institutions without compatibility issues.

The result of this rigorous analysis is a comprehensive data analysis document that outlines how data will be handled, protected, and utilised in the development of the acceleration services. This document is crucial for the next steps, particularly in ensuring that the technical aspects of service implementation are based on solid, actionable data insights.

Step 4: Business process definition (WP4)

This step, which fits in the Define Design Thinking phase, details the business processes that underpin the acceleration services. Utilising Business Process Modeling Language (BPML), the processes are formalised, capturing the workflows that will be automated or enhanced

through the acceleration services. This formalisation helps in creating a structured approach to service delivery, which is essential for consistent and efficient implementation.

A user guide is also developed during this phase. This guide is instrumental in helping less technical users understand how to utilise the new services effectively. It acts as a bridge, reducing the learning curve associated with adopting new technologies and processes.

The documentation produced in this step ensures that every aspect of the service's business process is clearly defined and accessible. This not only aids in the implementation phase but also ensures that stakeholders are fully informed about how the services will operate and impact their daily activities.

Step 5: Implementation (WP5)

The implementation phase, which fits to the Ideate and Prototype Design Thinking phase, is where the theoretical designs and plans become tangible services within the Agora environment. This environment leverages the Odoo open-source framework, chosen for its flexibility and the ability to integrate specific components necessary for tailoring services to the needs of HEIs.

The use of an open-source framework helps keep costs low, which is particularly beneficial for HEIs with smaller IT budgets. It also allows for greater customization and scalability, adapting to the unique requirements of different institutions without substantial additional investment.

The implementation phase not only involves the technical setup but also ensures that all components work together seamlessly. This includes extensive checking within the Agora environment to ensure that the services are robust, reliable, and ready for deployment across various HEIs.

Step 6: Testing and assessment (WP6)

Once the services are implemented, they undergo rigorous testing to ensure they meet the outlined specifications and stakeholder expectations, this step fits to the Test Design Thinking phase. Key performance indicators are established to measure the effectiveness, efficiency, and user satisfaction of the services. These indicators are crucial for gauging the success of the services and identifying areas for improvement.

Feedback from initial users is collected and analysed, providing valuable insights into how the services perform in real-world scenarios. This feedback loop is essential for iterative development, allowing for continuous refinement of the services based on actual user experiences.

The assessment phase is critical for validating the impact of the acceleration services on the academic community. It helps ensure that the services not only meet the technical specifications but also deliver real, measurable benefits to users and stakeholders.

Step 7: Dissemination (WP7)

The final step in the process involves disseminating the knowledge and insights gained throughout the development and implementation phases. This dissemination serves multiple purposes: it promotes the adoption of the services within and beyond the initial HEIs, it encourages continuous improvement of the services, and it supports the development of new services by sharing best practices and lessons learned.

Efforts in this phase include publishing case studies, conducting workshops, and participating in academic conferences to share the successes and challenges encountered. This not only enhances the visibility of the services but also fosters a collaborative community of practice that can contribute to further innovation and refinement of acceleration services in the higher education sector.

6 Acceleration service catalogue

In this section, we provide an initial catalogue of acceleration services, outlined in Table 6.1. The criteria to include them in this catalogue are that the acceleration service has been identified by the stakeholders as valuable and that it is feasible to offer this acceleration service through the Agora, some of them have already started to be co-created with the stakeholders.

Table 6.1. List of Acceleration Services

N°	Acceleration Service
1	Supply of Agoras tailored to HEIs' or Alliances' needs
2	Catalogue of research infrastructures and TTOs
3	Events, Conferences, and Workshops
4	Accessing Grants and Funding
5	Coaching and Support Mechanism for HEIs
6	Methodology for an Investment Strategy
7	Stakeholders management
8	Showcases

These services offer practical solutions to enhance collaboration, improve resource accessibility, and drive institutional progress. From tailored communication platforms like

Agoras to strategic investment methodologies, each service aims to address specific needs within the HEI ecosystem. Explore the detailed descriptions below to gain insights into how these services—Supply of Tailored Agoras, Catalogue of Research Infrastructures and TTOs, Events, Conferences, and Workshops, Accessing Grants and Funding, Coaching and Support Mechanism for HEIs, Methodology for Investment Strategy, Stakeholders Management, and Showcases—can benefit research, innovation, and institutional development.

The service package, according to Fitzsimmons (2011), is vital in service marketing and management, especially within acceleration services. It encompasses goods and services offered to customers within a specific context, aiding businesses in communicating their value. The catalogue outline comprises a table with rows corresponding to elements of the service package, which have been identified with the inputs of WP4 D4.1. It serves as a dynamic document continuously updated collaboratively. The subsequent description of table fields utilises these concepts.

Explicit services are the core, intangible services that customers receive when they engage with a service provider. Following ITIL terminology, these are the outcomes of the acceleration services, which are the primary benefits or experiences that customers seek. For example, the research and infrastructure notice board, to find peers to collaborate in a research proposal.

Information is a crucial component of the service package. It includes data, knowledge, and communication that is used to enhance and support the service. Information can be provided in various forms. For instance, the Agora may provide user guides and online support to assist customers in using their acceleration services.

Implicit services are the additional, often intangible, elements of the service that customers may not explicitly request but still contribute to their overall satisfaction. In the scope of acceleration service, we use the implicit services in the R&I areas of the Higher Education Transformation Agenda such as: (a) empowering HEIs towards developing shared R&I strategies that deliver on Europe's challenges with critical mass; (b) facilitate the sharing of capacity, infrastructure and resources through collaborative settings, such as the European Universities initiative; (c) improve the attractiveness of researchers' careers, including through reform of the career assessment and incentives regimes; (d) facilitate cooperation with surrounding R&I ecosystem actors; (e) support the transition to knowledge- and digitally-driven HEIs that mainstream Open Science practices and include research and innovation outputs in teaching; (f) engage citizens in solving societal challenges; (g) support institutional change through inclusive gender equality plans.

Supporting Facility refers to the physical or tangible infrastructure that is necessary to deliver the service. This can include the Agora, and other physical assets, such as rooms, for example.

Facilitating outputs are tangible or intangible deliverables of an activity that accompanies the service and enhances its value. These are typically provided to the customer as part of the

service. For example, in the shared research infrastructure it would be the physical research infrastructure.

Service offering is a formal description of one or more services, designed to address the needs of a target consumer group. The components of a service offering can be goods, access to resources and service actions, in which we describe the utility, that is the functionality offered by a product or service to meet a particular need.

Service providers encompass a diverse range of entities offering services, such as academia, administrative staff, technical experts, and members of the research and innovation ecosystem. Additionally, specific initiatives like the aUPaEU Project and the Agora(s) Online Services Platform(s) play crucial roles in delivering specialised services within their respective domains. These providers collectively contribute to meeting various needs and demands across educational, organisational, technical, and research landscapes.

Service consumers span a diverse spectrum, encompassing academia, administrative staff, technical experts, the research and innovation ecosystem, and society as a whole. These users engage with services offered by educational institutions, organisations' management personnel, technical support experts, and entities involved in research and innovation. Additionally, the broader society, comprising the general public and the community, forms an integral part of the user base, collectively benefiting from and contributing to the services provided across various domains.

Proposed indicators: We will validate the services described in the catalogue through interviews. WP6 testing activities, which focus not only qualitative but also quantitative measures such as indicators, will be dedicated to testing the implemented services. Indicators are used to measure the added value and effectiveness of the **shared activities** provided through the acceleration services. These indicators serve as measures to assess the impact and success of the services on various stakeholders and the overall ecosystem. They provide valuable insights into the progress and outcomes achieved through the implementation of the acceleration services.

6.1 Acceleration service #1: Supply of Agoras tailored to HEIs' or Alliances' needs

Agoras offer acceleration services by providing a collaborative platform where HEIs can access guidance, share knowledge, and receive support to accelerate their efforts towards institutional transformation and innovation. Moreover, Agora's intelligent recommendation algorithm facilitates partnerships by connecting HEIs with suitable collaborators, ensuring alignment with their specific transformation needs. As the core of the aUPaEU project, the Agora represents a paradigm shift in supporting HEI transformation by addressing information system fragmentation, offering value-added services, and facilitating stakeholder engagement across Europe.

This table provides a detailed description of the "Supply of Agoras tailored to HEIs' or Alliances' needs" acceleration service, emphasising its alignment with various outcomes and its role in delivering tailored digital tools for collaboration and communication within the higher education and research community.

<i>Explicit Services</i>	The primary benefit of this acceleration service is to provide tailor-made Agora platforms to meet the specific needs of higher education institutions (HEIs) and alliances, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.
<i>Information</i>	The service offers comprehensive information, including user guides and online support, to assist HEIs and alliances in effectively utilising the customised Agora platforms.
<i>Implicit Services</i>	This service aligns with multiple outcomes, including facilitating collaborations between HEIs, enhancing cooperation with the R&I ecosystem, promoting the attractiveness of researchers' careers, advancing gender equality, engaging citizens in research, sharing research resources and infrastructures, and promoting digitalization in HEIs. The service's customization and support contribute to these implicit services.
<i>Supporting Facility</i>	The supporting facility involves the development and maintenance of the Agora platform, including the necessary digital infrastructure and hosting services.
<i>Facilitating Outputs</i>	Tangible deliverables include the customised Agora platform, which serves as a digital tool for live human interaction and communication, access to resources, and support for production and supply services tailored to HEIs' or alliances' needs.
<i>Service Offering</i>	The service offering is a description of the tailor-made Agora platforms designed to address the specific requirements of HEIs and alliances. It encompasses digital tools for live interaction,

	resource access, and production and supply services, facilitating collaboration and knowledge sharing.
<i>Service Providers</i>	Service providers for this acceleration service include academia, administrative staff, and the R&I ecosystem, who collaborate in developing and customising Agora platforms.
<i>Service Consumers</i>	Service consumers encompass academia, administrative staff, technical staff, the R&I ecosystem, and society as a whole. HEIs and alliances benefit from tailored Agora platforms, enabling knowledge exchange and collaboration, while society benefits from the outcomes of enhanced research and cooperation.
<i>Proposed Indicators</i>	Numbers of users according to the type of stakeholders for each service (see D7.1)

Specifically, two examples of this service are [Unite! Alliance Agora](#) and [EPICUR Alliance Agora](#).

Shared infrastructures
Facilitate access to shared research infrastructures among partners to encourage their researchers to utilize these facilities

Showcases
Share outcomes and insights that provide best practices and experiences to support broader global outreach

Stakeholder handling
Empower to effectively manage engagement with stakeholders in support of digital transformation

R&I notice board
Proposal ideas, development of your R&I profile, and forming research collaborations, project consortia and seed funding

Co-funded by the
ERACUR Programme
of the European Union

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Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
programme under grant agreement No. 101019223

6.2 Acceleration service #2: Catalogue of research infrastructures and TTOs

This table provides a detailed description of an example acceleration service, highlighting how it aligns with the provided concepts and serves as a model for other acceleration services in your catalogue.

<i>Explicit Services</i>	The core benefit of this acceleration service is to connect researchers for collaboration.
<i>Information</i>	The service offers user guides and online support for researchers using the Agora platform.
<i>Implicit Services</i>	This service aligns with the Higher Education Transformation Agenda by empowering HEIs to develop shared R&I strategies and enhancing the attractiveness of researchers' careers through collaboration and Open Science practices.
<i>Supporting Facility</i>	The supporting facility includes the Agora platform, dedicated online spaces, and collaboration rooms.
<i>Facilitating Outputs</i>	Tangible deliverables include access to the Agora platform, collaboration spaces, and virtual research environments.
<i>Service Offering</i>	The service offering describes a platform for research collaboration, offering access to online collaboration spaces, data sharing, and project management tools, facilitating efficient research collaboration among HEIs.
<i>Service Providers</i>	Service providers for this acceleration service include academia, technical experts, and the Agora support services.
<i>Service Consumers</i>	Service consumers encompass academia and research and innovation ecosystem members, facilitating knowledge exchange and collaboration among a diverse user base.
<i>Proposed Indicators</i>	The number of faculty members external to the university that owns the research infrastructure (i) that connects to a description of the research infrastructure and (ii) that will apply to use the infrastructure.

A practical example of the "#2: Catalogue of Research Infrastructures and TTOs" service is the [Unite! Research infrastructures catalogue](#). It provides detailed information on each research infrastructure, including descriptions, website links, contact details, availability of technical support, and online booking options. This tool promotes collaboration among

alliance partners by enabling tracking and feedback of the access to equipment and training across universities, obtaining information from the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and other data platforms.

6.3 Acceleration service #3: Events, Conferences, and Workshops

This table provides a detailed description of the "Events, Conferences, and Workshops" acceleration service, emphasising its role in facilitating live human interaction and communication to achieve various outcomes, along with the potential for AI integration to enhance user engagement and tailor event experiences.

<p><i>Explicit Services</i></p>	<p>This acceleration service focused on organising and facilitating events, conferences, and workshops that foster collaboration between higher education institutions (HEIs), promote cooperation with the R&I ecosystem, enhance the attractiveness of researchers' careers, advance gender equality, engage citizens in research, and</p>
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	encourage the sharing of research resources and infrastructures. The explicit service involves the coordination and execution of these events to achieve specific outcomes.
<i>Information</i>	The service provides comprehensive information about upcoming events, conferences, and workshops, including details, schedules, and registration processes. Additionally, it may offer AI-integrated features to identify users' scientific interests and tailor event recommendations and communications accordingly.
<i>Implicit Services</i>	Implicit services encompass a wide range of outcomes driven by the nature and focus of the events. These outcomes may include increased collaboration between HEIs, improved cooperation with the R&I ecosystem, enhanced attractiveness of researchers' careers, progress in gender equality, heightened citizen involvement in research, and greater sharing of research resources and infrastructures. The customization potential through AI integration enhances the user experience and engagement.
<i>Supporting Facility</i>	The supporting facility includes the organisational infrastructure for planning, promoting, and hosting events, conferences, and workshops. This infrastructure ensures smooth event execution, venue management, and participant engagement.
<i>Facilitating Outputs</i>	Tangible outputs consist of well-organised and executed events, conferences, and workshops that facilitate live human interaction and communication among academia, administrative staff, technical staff, the R&I ecosystem, and society. AI integration, if employed, generates tailored event recommendations and communications.
<i>Service Offering</i>	The service offering describes the provision of events, conferences, and workshops that align with the goals of collaboration, cooperation, gender equality, and citizen involvement. It encompasses the customization of event experiences and AI integration to identify users' scientific interests for personalised engagement.
<i>Service Providers</i>	Service providers for this acceleration service include academia, administrative staff, and technical staff responsible for planning and organising events. AI integration experts may also be involved in enhancing user engagement through technology.
<i>Service Consumers</i>	Service consumers represent academia, administrative staff,

	technical staff, the R&I ecosystem, and society. HEIs, researchers, and the broader community benefit from participating in these events, gaining opportunities for collaboration, knowledge exchange, and career advancement. AI-enhanced engagement benefits users seeking tailored event experiences.
<i>Proposed Indicators</i>	Number/ Category of workshops/events organised together by the partners(i), the number of different topics addressed by the events (ii) and the number of faculty, master and PhD students that will participate to such events, per year (iii)

Although the technical platform for Acceleration Service #3: Events, Conferences, and Workshops are ready, the service itself has not yet been fully deployed. Initially, a few examples are provided, as illustrated in the figure below ([link](#)). Past events like the '[Biomass Winter School](#)' organised by Unite! and upcoming events such as the '[Unite! Research School](#)' in Autumn 2024 stands to benefit from this service, showcasing its potential utility in fostering collaboration, promoting engagement with the R&I ecosystem, and advancing various strategic goals.

The screenshot shows the Unite! website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Unite! logo, 'Home', 'Acceleration Services', 'Sign in', and 'Contact Us'. Below the navigation bar, there is a search bar and a '← All Events' link. The main content area features a large banner for an event titled 'Level up your outreach skills: power networking and cool communication for students'. Below the banner, there is a light blue bar with the text 'Registrations are closed' and a red button that says 'Registrations Closed'. The event details are presented in a grid layout:

- Join us for this 2-hour event**: This webinar will help you improve your communication skills when working with non-specialist audiences such as prospective students, civil society organisations, citizens, small and medium enterprises, or public administrations. The aim is to identify and understand the opportunities of working with non-specialist audiences and propose ways to reach them and work together for dissemination but also co-creation of knowledge.
- DATE & TIME**: Tuesday 21 November 2023, 17:00 → 19:00, Europe/Brussels. There is an 'Add to Calendar' button.
- ORGANISER**: (UPC) UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA, Aina Tella Arbos.

Additional text on the page includes: 'After registration you will receive all the information required to facilitate your participation' and 'With your participation in the webinar, you give your consent that there will be screenshots and the meeting will be recorded'.

6.4 Acceleration service #4: Accessing Grants and Funding

This table provides a detailed description of the "Accessing Grants and Funding" acceleration service, highlighting its role in providing access to European calls, enhancing research collaboration, and leveraging AI technology to recommend relevant grants and funding opportunities to users, while also offering human support when needed.

<i>Explicit Services</i>	This acceleration service focuses on providing access to European calls for grants and funding opportunities. It aims to foster collaborations between higher education institutions (HEIs) and enhance the attractiveness of researchers' careers. The explicit service involves granting users access to grant and funding opportunities through European calls.
<i>Information</i>	The service offers comprehensive information about available grants and funding opportunities, including details, eligibility criteria, and application deadlines. It also employs AI technology for recommending grants and funding options tailored to users' research interests and profiles.
<i>Implicit Services</i>	Implicit services encompass the promotion of collaboration between HEIs, as researchers access grants for joint projects, and the advancement of researchers' careers by securing funding for their work. The AI-integrated recommendation system enhances users' chances of finding relevant opportunities and streamlines the application process.
<i>Supporting Facility</i>	The supporting facility includes the digital infrastructure and platform that host grant and funding information, as well as the AI recommendation system. This infrastructure ensures efficient access to opportunities and personalised recommendations.
<i>Facilitating Outputs</i>	Tangible outputs consist of access to a wide range of European grants and funding opportunities, AI-generated grant recommendations, and resources for preparing and submitting applications. Human support and communication are also available when needed to assist users in navigating the application process.
<i>Service Offering</i>	The service offering describes the provision of access to European calls for grants and funding. It includes the AI-driven recommendation of grants based on users' research interests, as well as human support and communication options for guidance during the application process.

<i>Service Providers</i>	Service providers for this acceleration service are likely to include academia and the R&I ecosystem. They play a key role in curating and presenting grant information, as well as developing and maintaining the AI recommendation system.
<i>Service Consumers</i>	Service consumers primarily consist of academia and administrative staff seeking grants and funding opportunities for research projects. Additionally, the R&I ecosystem benefits from collaborations facilitated by access to funding. Users receive tailored recommendations and support through AI integration and human communication.
<i>Proposed Indicators</i>	Number of collaborative projects created via this service Number of responses and overall time to obtain them

One example of this service is the Unite! [R&I notice board](#) co-created jointly with the [IRIS network](#), offering a proposals' platform for collaboration within the alliance. These initiatives address challenges such as difficulty in finding partners for events, and they will streamline access to European calls for grants and funding opportunities, enhancing collaboration and supporting researchers' careers effectively. Additionally, the integration of AIDA, the Agora AI recommendation system, will further streamline the process of obtaining complementary information from the CORDIS platform ,among others.

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01

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Battery - Electrical storage (Abuse tests) - until 2024-05-17

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2024-07-31

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6.5 Acceleration service #5: Coaching and Support Mechanism for HEIs

This table provides a detailed description of the "Coaching and Support Mechanism for HEIs" acceleration service, emphasising its role in facilitating institutional transformation across multiple areas while tailoring coaching and support to the specific needs of HEIs and stakeholders.

<p><i>Explicit Services</i></p>	<p>This acceleration service focuses on offering coaching and support to higher education institutions (HEIs) to drive institutional transformation in various areas. It encompasses assistance in accessing funding, implementing acceleration services, addressing specific challenges, developing leadership skills, and connecting participatory projects to different stakeholders. The explicit service involves tailored coaching and support based on the specific needs of HEIs and stakeholders.</p>
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<i>Information</i>	The service provides comprehensive information about the areas of institutional transformation, available support services, and resources. It offers guidance and educational materials to aid HEIs in their transformation efforts.
<i>Implicit Services</i>	Implicit services include facilitating HEI transformation in multiple areas, enhancing their ability to access funding, successfully implement acceleration services, overcome challenges, develop leadership skills, and establish connections with various stakeholders. The service is customised to address specific needs, fostering growth and development within HEIs.
<i>Supporting Facility</i>	The supporting facility encompasses the infrastructure for delivering coaching and support services. It includes digital platforms, educational resources, and access to expertise from academia, the research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem, and administrative staff.
<i>Facilitating Outputs</i>	Tangible outputs consist of tailored coaching and support programs, access to educational resources, guidance for accessing funding, successful implementation of acceleration services, solutions for addressing challenges, leadership development, and established connections with stakeholders.
<i>Service Offering</i>	The service offering describes the provision of coaching and support to HEIs in areas such as funding access, acceleration service implementation, challenge resolution, leadership development, and stakeholder engagement. It emphasises customization to meet the unique needs of each HEI and stakeholder group.
<i>Service Providers</i>	Service providers for this acceleration service encompass academia, the R&I ecosystem, and administrative staff who offer expertise and guidance in various transformation areas. They collaborate to deliver tailored support to HEIs and stakeholders.
<i>Service Consumers</i>	Service consumers include HEIs seeking guidance and support for institutional transformation in areas like funding access, acceleration service implementation, challenge resolution, leadership development, and stakeholder engagement. Stakeholders involved in HEI transformation processes also benefit from the service's customization and expertise.
<i>Proposed Indicators</i>	Number of services proposed to HEI to facilitate institutional transformation (i) and the number of HEI that will use them (ii). The services range from providing examples of documents to facilitate collaborative work, or preparing analysis of the socio-economical environment of the HEI, to exchanging staff to facilitate the collective transformation of HEIs or addressing groups of

	stakeholders in different socio-economical environments at the same time, together.
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WP4 of the aUPaEU project will craft coaching and guidance mechanisms to aid HEIs and alliances in embracing digital transformation. This acceleration service, #5: Coaching and Support Mechanism for HEIs, will be integrated into the open Agora, which is presently in the ideation phase alongside sister projects CATALISI and Accelerate Future HEI. D4.1 outlines initial pathways to address common challenges by defining preliminary business processes and offering recommendations.

6.6 Acceleration service #6: Methodology for an Investment Strategy

This table provides a detailed description of the "Methodology for an Investment Strategy" acceleration service, highlighting its role in assisting HEIs and ecosystem stakeholders in planning, accessing funding, and executing transformations while fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange within the HEI and ecosystem network.

<i>Explicit Services</i>	This acceleration service offers a comprehensive methodology to support higher education institutions (HEIs) and the surrounding ecosystem in developing an investment strategy to facilitate access to funding and deliver on chosen transformations. It provides a structured framework for identifying needs, creating transformation roadmaps, mapping funding sources, and evaluating progress. The explicit service aims to empower HEIs and ecosystem stakeholders to strategically plan and execute transformations.
<i>Information</i>	The service includes a knowledge base that serves as a repository of information and best practices related to institutional transformation. It offers valuable insights through case studies, success stories, and lessons learned. The knowledge base assists HEIs and stakeholders in making informed decisions throughout the investment strategy development process.
<i>Implicit Services</i>	Implicit services encompass the facilitation of HEI and ecosystem transformation through a methodical approach. By utilising the methodology, users can better understand their needs, create actionable roadmaps, identify funding opportunities, and establish mechanisms for progress evaluation. Implicit services contribute to fostering innovation and knowledge exchange within HEIs and their ecosystem.

<i>Supporting Facility</i>	The supporting facility consists of a virtual meeting place where HEIs, ecosystem stakeholders, experts, and peers can collaborate and exchange insights. It serves as a platform for networking, knowledge sharing, and mutual support, enhancing the effectiveness of the methodology.
<i>Facilitating Outputs</i>	Tangible outputs include well-defined transformation roadmaps, identification of suitable funding sources, access to the knowledge base's valuable resources, and the establishment of collaborative connections within the HEI and ecosystem network. These outputs facilitate the implementation of chosen transformations.
<i>Service Offering</i>	The service offering describes the provision of a structured methodology to develop an investment strategy for HEIs and their surrounding ecosystem. It emphasises the importance of informed decision-making, transformation planning, funding accessibility, and progress assessment.
<i>Service Providers</i>	Service providers for this acceleration service comprise experts and stakeholders from academia, the research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem, and administrative staff. They collaborate to offer guidance, insights, and support in utilising the methodology effectively.
<i>Service Consumers</i>	Service consumers are HEIs and stakeholders within the ecosystem seeking to advance institutional transformation and access funding for chosen initiatives. These users benefit from the structured methodology, knowledge base, and networking opportunities provided by the service.
<i>Proposed Indicators</i>	Number/ Category of users?

WP3 will offer a vision of digital support and a consulting infrastructure to formulate investment plans for HEIs, networks of HEIs, or alliances. It aims to integrate collaboration tools to facilitate scientist-to-scientist, HEI-to-HEI, and network-to-network relations to identify funding opportunities for common research topics. This acceleration service, labelled as #6: Methodology for an Investment Strategy, will be embedded into the open Agora, currently in the ideation phase with sister projects CATALISI and Accelerate Future HEI.

6.7 Acceleration service #7: Stakeholders management

This table provides a comprehensive description of the "Stakeholders Management" acceleration service, emphasising its role in effectively managing a diverse range of stakeholders involved in the HEIs acceleration services project. The service aims to foster

collaboration, align interests, and ensure project success by developing clear stakeholder engagement strategies and facilitating communication and conflict resolution.

<i>Explicit Services</i>	This acceleration service focuses on the effective management of stakeholders involved in the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) acceleration services project. It encompasses the development of a clear stakeholder engagement strategy to identify key stakeholders, define their roles and responsibilities, and establish communication channels. The service aims to ensure that the project is successful and that the developed services are relevant and beneficial to all stakeholders.
<i>Information</i>	Information within this service involves the collection, analysis, and dissemination of data related to stakeholders. It includes data on stakeholder interests, objectives, and behaviour, facilitating informed decision-making and communication.
<i>Implicit Services</i>	Implicit services encompass the facilitation of collaboration, conflict resolution, and alignment of stakeholder interests. They involve managing conflict, fostering communication, and ensuring that the needs and interests of all stakeholders are considered in decision-making processes. Implicit services contribute to a harmonious and productive stakeholder engagement process.
<i>Supporting Facility</i>	The supporting facility in this context involves tools and platforms for stakeholder engagement and communication. It includes digital platforms, communication channels, and collaboration tools to facilitate interaction and information sharing among stakeholders.
<i>Facilitating Outputs</i>	Tangible outputs of this service include a well-defined stakeholder engagement strategy, stakeholder data analysis reports, conflict resolution outcomes, and collaborative initiatives. These outputs contribute to effective stakeholder management and project success.
<i>Service Offering</i>	The service offering describes the provision of stakeholder management services tailored to the needs of the HEIs acceleration services project. It emphasises the importance of stakeholder engagement, alignment, and collaboration.
<i>Service Providers</i>	Service providers for this acceleration service encompass a wide range of stakeholders involved in the HEIs acceleration services project. This includes HEIs themselves, networks of universities, the European Commission, Member States, investors, and public funders, who collectively contribute to successful stakeholder management.
<i>Service Consumers</i>	Service consumers are primarily the HEIs and their associated stakeholders participating in the acceleration services. These consumers benefit from effective stakeholder management, which

	ensures that project services are relevant, beneficial, and sustainable.
<i>Proposed Indicators</i>	Number of contact with external stakeholders facilitated by the acceleration services (i) and the number of activities established between HEI and external stakeholders (ii).

In the aUPaEU Project, stakeholder management is a vital component, involving diverse entities citizens, HEIs and research institutions, university alliances, HEI and research institutions networks, public administration, and industry and businesses (Table 3.1 of D7.1). Stakeholders management is one of the business processes described in the section 3 of the deliverable D4.1.

The Agora will be used to increase and improve the involvement of external stakeholders in HEI activities. This is especially useful for stakeholders who do not have access to the knowledge and databases owned by HEIs. Examples of such groups are citizen associations who do not have access to scientific information or to networks of scientific specialised in a particular domain, economic networks of companies who would like to address collectively a technological question, or who are looking for specific trainings not yet addressed by continuous formation, institutions seeking advices and recommendations on practical aspects, or formation to specific competences. The practical advantage of the Agora is its accessibility, and the possibility to connect, in a controlled manner, to more specialised tools, such as the [Metacampus of the Unite! Alliance](#) for training.

Another practical example of the stakeholder management implementation is the CRM of the Unite! Agora, containing more than 1000 stakeholders and processing more that 300 enquiries so far.

Pipeline

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New	Qualified	Proposition
<p>Open Educational Resources (OER) in Higher Education (MOOC)</p> <p>(TU GRAZ) TECHNISCHE UNIVERS...</p> <p>Mooc</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Agora and Unite! Cm3 Virtual Inclusion Office WG</p> <p>(ULISBOA) UNIVERSIDADE DE LIS...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Showcase for everything related to Unite! staff</p> <p>(Grenoble INP - UGA) INSTITUT DI...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>
<p>Unite! Open Educational Resources in Higher Education</p> <p>(TU GRAZ) TECHNISCHE UNIVERS...</p> <p>course</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Vladimir is seeking a Partner for Unite! Seed Fund</p> <p>(TU GRAZ) TECHNISCHE UNIVERS...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>(test) AWESOME MOOC</p> <p>(Aalto) AALTO UNIVERSITY, Meliss...</p> <p>Mooc</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>
<p>CoDaS Master's Programme in Communications Engineering and Data Science (Erasmus Mundus)</p> <p>(Aalto) AALTO UNIVERSITY, Ella La...</p> <p>Joint Master's & Double Degree</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Regular report for Technical Commission 11.12.2023 at 11 Vienna time</p> <p>(UPC) aUPaEU, Jesus Alcobér</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Interest from Victoria about Battery - Electrical storage (Abuse tests)</p> <p>(UPC) UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>
<p>Certificate - webinar</p> <p>(WROCLAW TECH) WROCLAW UNI...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Interest from Jaume about Battery - Electrical storage (Abuse tests)</p> <p>(UPC) UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Wind turbine power curve optimization via Active Flow Control</p> <p>(UPC) UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>
<p>Cleaning up CommUnitees on the Metacampus</p> <p>(TU GRAZ) TECHNISCHE UNIVERS...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Unite! agora workshop in Graz Dialogue</p> <p>(TU GRAZ) TECHNISCHE UNIVERS...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>"Removal strategy" for finished / inactive Metacampus courses</p> <p>technical commission</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>
<p>Enquiry of change in example</p> <p>(UPC) UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Internships-Aalto summer research Programme</p> <p>(Aalto) AALTO UNIVERSITY, Eija Ku...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Crossroads of Speech and Laguage - Teaching and Research Seed Fund Projects</p> <p>(TU GRAZ) TECHNISCHE UNIVERS...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>
<p>Metacampus course "Unite! Student Festival Lisbon 2023"</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Test</p> <p>(UPC) aUPaEU, Alba Roma</p> <p>course</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Unite! 6.4 uncovering the space, setting an Agora form and email requests</p> <p>(WROCLAW TECH) WROCLAW UNI...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>
<p>Metacampus course "Unite! Joint Programs"</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Wellbeing buddies</p> <p>(UPC) UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA...</p> <p>course</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Test space for user testing from Kjell Carli</p> <p>(KTH) KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOEG...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>
<p>Metacampus course "Student co-creation Unite!4future"</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Re: Next steps with Agora repository and form</p> <p>(Aalto) AALTO UNIVERSITY, Meliss...</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	
<p>Test</p> <p>(UPC) aUPaEU, Alba Roma</p> <p>Joint Master's & Double Degree</p> <p>☆☆☆ ○ ●</p>	<p>Molecules and Materials at</p>	

6.8 Acceleration service #8: Showcases

This table provides a comprehensive description of the "Showcases" acceleration service, highlighting its role in creating agile platforms for HEIs to showcase collaborative initiatives. The service aims to engage stakeholders, share resources, and gather feedback through user-friendly websites that facilitate effective presentation and interaction.

Explicit Services

The "Showcases" acceleration service offers a set of easily deployable websites that serve as agile tools for showcasing collaborative initiatives among multiple higher education institutions (HEIs). These websites allow stakeholders to access specific resources aligned with their interests, manage inquiries and interests, and provide feedback through satisfaction surveys. The

	service's primary focus is on creating platforms for presenting collaborative efforts effectively.
<i>Information</i>	Information within this service involves the content and data presented on the showcase websites. It includes resources, inquiries, feedback, and related information shared on these platforms. Information is organised and curated to facilitate stakeholders' access and engagement.
<i>Implicit Services</i>	Implicit services encompass the facilitation of stakeholder engagement and interaction through the showcase websites. These services include features that encourage collaboration, resource sharing, and feedback collection. Implicit services aim to enhance the overall user experience and satisfaction.
<i>Supporting Facility</i>	The supporting facility for this service includes the websites themselves, which are the digital platforms where the showcases are hosted. These websites provide the infrastructure for stakeholders to access information, engage with resources, and submit inquiries and feedback.
<i>Facilitating Outputs</i>	Tangible outputs of this service comprise the functioning showcase websites, populated with relevant content and resources. Additionally, the service may generate reports based on stakeholder feedback and interactions, helping HEIs assess the impact of their collaborative efforts.
<i>Service Offering</i>	The service offering describes the provision of showcase websites that HEIs can use to highlight their collaborative initiatives. It emphasises the importance of effective presentation, stakeholder engagement, and feedback collection.
<i>Service Providers</i>	Service providers for the "Showcases" acceleration service are HEIs and other organisations that utilise the showcase websites to display their collaborative efforts. These providers contribute content, resources, and engagement opportunities to the showcases.
<i>Service Consumers</i>	Service consumers encompass a wide range of stakeholders, including HEIs, their staff and students, partners in collaborative initiatives, and external stakeholders interested in the showcased efforts. These consumers benefit from easy access to information, resources, and engagement opportunities provided by the showcases.
<i>Proposed Indicators</i>	Number of users / Category of users Number of connections

An illustrative example of the "#8: Showcases" acceleration service is a dedicated platform within Unite! Alliance specifically designed for [Faculty and staff](#). This platform enables teachers, researchers, and administrative and technical staff, young researchers members to connect with others who share similar interests, internationalise their professional curriculum, seek partners for teaching, research, or university management projects, and participate in socialising clubs.

7 Conclusion

The aUPaEU project, under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aims to accelerate the transformation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Europe. It involves a collaboration of five renowned universities, focusing on creating an acceleration services catalogue as part of Deliverable D2.1. This catalogue offers a range of services, from custom digital platforms (Agoras) to research infrastructures and HEI support mechanisms, to enhance research collaboration and innovation across the European Research Area. The project emphasises stakeholder engagement and comparative analysis to continually evolve its services. It represents a significant step towards fostering a unified European Research and Innovation landscape, setting a standard for future educational and research transformations in Europe.

In conclusion, it is essential to acknowledge that this initial set of acceleration services represents just the beginning of our journey. As we move forward, our strategy, methodology, and catalogue will evolve in response to changing needs, emerging trends, and feedback from stakeholders.

The indicators will be implemented in the acceleration services and will be monitored to improve those services.

We started with core stakeholders, including academia and project partners, laying a strong foundation for our work. However, our commitment to inclusivity drives us to expand our outreach to include extended stakeholders, such as students, industry partners, and community members.

Our next steps involve contacting FOR-EU for valuable insights into European projects and higher education policies, creating and implementing surveys to gather broader perspectives, and fostering collaboration with diverse stakeholders. Additionally, we aim to continuously refine our methodology, leveraging lessons learned from other alliances and projects, and adapting to the dynamic landscape of higher education. WP6 will validate each service idea described in the acceleration services catalogue involving prospective and current users. The focus is on verifying whether the services meet their needs and assessing if the solution effectively and efficiently addresses them. Depending on the results, we will understand if a service is ready to proceed with the platform implementation (WP5) or may find that the concept needs refinement to appeal to our potential users. By embracing a collaborative and forward-thinking approach, we are poised to develop innovative solutions that meet the evolving needs of higher education institutions and contribute to their success.

8 References

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